

Optimizing data to make more efficient and effective business decisions

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Knowing what to do with mass volumes of data is nothing more than a monumental task, especially when the user base are not Data Scientists but rather everyday employees. It is pivotal now more than ever that all levels of leadership can access data and data insights to make more well-informed decisions to help manage costs and growth.

2. Aim

Take millions of line items of useless data and make it user-friendly with prediction models to prioritize areas of focus and make more well-informed decisions during the sales cycle

3. Materials And Methods:

Leverage data from multiple systems and converge into a single super computer with prediction modeling codes to determine customers likelihood to repurchase services.

4. Results:

Millions of data records leveraged and 650 unique data points were used to provide a simplified view of a customers' environment with prediction accuracy for likelihood to repurchase at an 88% accuracy level.

5. Conclusions:

When the data was leveraged by the sales organization the Service renewal rates were 20% higher than when not used. It saved sales valuable time during the sales cycle and provided customers with unique insights about their account which they were not previously aware of.

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6. Keywords:

Big Data, Vertica Servers, Web based interface, Machine learning

Author biography

Debora Bielecki has led multi-billion dollar businesses globally through enterprise transformation and innovation, leveraging Big Data and Artificial Intelligence — achieving improved contract renewal performance, a \$500M cost reduction within a services supply chain and a \$250M reduction in warranty costs and recovery. Her worldwide experience extends to the Americas, Europe, the Middle East, Africa and the Asia-Pacific.

Debora has also defined and led multiple go-to-market strategies that have exceeded corporate goals. She invented and deployed a big data, predictive analytics solution (patent-pending) that predicts customers' services' needs. This gives unprecedented data insight to help teams make strategic sales decisions. Debora was awarded the Technology Services Innovation Award for this achievement at Hewlett-Packard.

A Partner at Bielecki & Associates, Debora is a management consultant and speaks frequently about big data, transformational strategy and new business models. She is a Co-Chair of the Canadian Advisory Council for Springboard Enterprises an accelerator for women led businesses seeking funding and advisory services, also an Advisory Board member for Women Get on Board, a member of the West Deane Restoration Effort, and a Grants Advisor for the Mississauga Swimming and Aquatic Club. Recognized for giving back to her community, Debora was awarded the City of Toronto's Volunteer Award in 2013, 2014, 2015 and 2016.